

CMIP Variable Priorities

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Background

WGCM 2019 endorsed concept of enhanced requirements for specification of priority 1 variables, including information on credible ranges and samples from models (this would, intentionally, make it difficult to put a variable at priority 1 if it has not been requested as part of a previous CMIP exercise at a lower priority and been provided by a reasonable range of models).

The specification of priorities in CMIP6 was as follows:

- 1: Modelling centres must commit to supplying all priority 1 variables associated with at least one science question for Tier 1 experiments of any MIP which they participate in;
- 2: Expected to be used in multi-model diagnostics; models not supplying these variables may be omitted from some parts of the inter-comparison;
- 3: Experimental -- used for exploring new capabilities and/or unlikely to be used in multi-model diagnostic.

In practise, many priority one variables are only provided for a limited range of models, so the commitment implicit in the above specification is meaningless. The approach used in CMIP6 means that those specifying the priority are not compelled to consider the resource implications, and modelling centres committing to participation are making statements of intent rather than binding promises.

To reset the process, all CMIP6 priority 2 variables will be shifted to the lowest priority, along with the existing priority 3 variables. Priority 1 variables will be moved to the "medium" priority unless they meet the new requirements for the top priority.

The aim is to shift from the current distribution of 60% at priority 1, 25% at 2 and 15% at 3 to 10% at high priority, 50% at medium and 40% at low.

Revised vocabulary for variable prioritisation.

The revised vocabulary has four terms, "high", "medium", "low".

High

High priority variables **MUST** have a citable reference document (constructed from reviewed metadata) setting out experience and expectations. This **MUST** include specification of acceptable and guide ranges for the data. It **MAY** include reference to results from previous CMIP cycles.

The reference document **MUST** include date of publication, author and review information.

If a requesting organisation cannot gather the required information, a variable may be included at a lower priority with intended_priority set to 'high'.

High priority should be used on variables which are required for the evaluation of basic model performance. It should not be used for variables needed for MIP specific process studies. Modelling centres wishing to support MIP specific process studies should provide medium priority variables for the associated MIPs.

Medium

Medium priority variables must have the following metadata reviewed and confirmed, in addition to the requirements specified for low priority variables: standard name, cell methods.

The description should be reviewed by at least one modeling centre or data centre.

If a requesting organisation cannot gather the required information, a variable may be included at a lower priority with intended_priority set to 'medium'.

If a variable is essential for completion of an analysis which a MIP intends to complete, it should be specified as priority medium or higher.

Low

Low priority variables must have the following meta data set:
variable name, title, units, proposed standard name, description.

Variables which are being introduced for added value or to support exploration of behaviour in processes represented in a limited number of models should be set at priority low.

Example for high priority: Daily, instantaneous tasmin.

Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature

Description

Daily minimum near surface air temperature provides a grid point value for each day representing the minimum of the near-surface air temperature for a 24 hour period from 00:00Z to 24:00Z.

Metadata

In this section constraints on attributes are given, expressed in the form "ClassName(value)", where the ClassName indicates the Data Type (see data type list[to do]).

units: Units("K");

standard_name: StandardName("air_temperature");

coordinates: Height("near_surface");

cell_methods: CellMethods("area: mean time: minimum")

Guidance

Data SHOULD be in the range guide range 170K to 230K.

Data values outside this range MUST be documented in the CMIP Errata service.

Data values MUST be in the strict range 120K to 260K.

Limits on mean absolute values to do.

Evidence

Daily near surface minimum temperature was provided by <many> models in CMIP6 and previous CMIP exercises. One model has data values outside the guide range in historical simulations. One has confirmed that an errata will be posted

The data values outside the guide range result from extreme tendencies generated by the model convection scheme which result in instantaneous values of temperature which are unrealistic. These values are corrected at the next model time-step.

The whiskers plot (below) based on the CMIP6 historical multi-model ensemble shows a high level of consistency.

Figure: Whiskers plot for the distribution of daily minimum near surface air temperature in the historical simulations of the CMIP6 archive. Models arranged alphabetically by institute and model. [AS-RCEC data has been revised since this plot was created]. For version information see [day.tasmin overview](#).

Commentary

In the CMIP6 data request this variable carried the description: '*minimum near-surface (usually, 2 meter) air temperature (add cell_method attribute "time: min")*', and did not have any guide values. The one-line description works, in a sense, because most data producers are familiar with the variable from past exercises and do not need clear information from the variable description. However, when it comes to sharing the data with a wider audience, a clearer description will be required.

The figure needs provenance information, e.g. linking to handle records. This could be done through a dataset containing the extrema ... e.g. a netcdf file at CEDA or a pdf + json in Zenodo. Zenodo is better suited to depositing grey literature to back up reference data. CEDA aims at reference data [is this a fair split?].

Example for Medium Priority

Tendency of Specific Humidity Due to Boundary Layer Mixing (monthly mean)

(CMIP6 variable tnhuspbl.Emon).

Description

Includes all boundary layer terms including diffusive terms.

Metadata

[CMIP6 metadat is OK]

Commentary

As with many variables, the description is sparse and cannot be used on its own. It needs someone to spend ten minutes composing a paragraph. For 1000 variables, that would imply a significant amount of work (slightly over 1 staff month), but far less than the work expended on producing data files. Split across 20 MIPs, this would imply around 1.5 days effort per MIP, on average.